

THE DOMINANT MODEL OF COMMUNICATION IN TRADITIONAL TEACHING AND MODERN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEMS

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Abstract:

The traditional school system included adopting as much information without critical thinking while modern school tends to democratic education that is focused on the development of individual abilities of each student and to develop his critical thinking. In traditional teaching communication the teacher dominates. Such is the autocratic communication which was reflected in a bossy role of teachers while in modern teaching the emphasis is on the student's role and the democratic communication. In pursuing the goal of non-experimental empirical research that we set in our study, we found that there is a statistically significant connection between interpersonal communication in teaching and students' success, and that those students whose teachers mostly used the democratic model of communication in teaching achieved statistically significantly better school achievements than those students whose teachers use mainly the autocratic model of communication. The survey was conducted in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Herzegovina-Neretva Canton) and a sample of 423 respondents (322 students and 101 teachers of primary schools). Through the results, contents and messages of this paper we have tried to make you aware of the importance of this segment of communication in the learning process and as such to make it the subject of everyday questioning and continuous work that should lead to its improvement, and thus to improving the quality of the entire educational process.

Keywords: communication, education, communication skills, quality teaching

1. Introduction

Communication between students and teachers, i.e. communication between all subjects of the teaching process is an important factor in quality schools. Students in

quality schools use democratic means of communication, and achieve better results in learning. To help the students learn to work well, it is necessary to understand that to us all the quality of life is extremely important. Quality school claims that all people have five basic needs: love, power, freedom, fun and survival. Quality is everything that meets one or more basic needs. The success of students in school is better if the school has quality. Quality school implies a democratic school, democratic form of communication, taking into account all the participants of the educational process. Caspe (2003) believes that the preparation of teachers in professional development programs should actively promote the development of communication skills for teachers. Lunenburg (2010) investigated the factors that may facilitate or impede the process of communication and its impact on the effectiveness of teaching.

He noted four categories of barriers to effective communication: process barriers, physical barriers, semantic barriers and psychological barriers, and he stressed the active listening as one of the conditions of successful teaching. The tendency of modern school is for students to be active participants in all phases of the teaching process, the aim is quality work which is based on a democratic, open and stimulating pedagogical communication. Today the teacher should not be only a teacher and evaluator, but more and more a planner, programmer, diagnostician, researcher, organizer, guide, innovator, advisor and educator. The more the teacher implements these modern functions his style of work is less classic authoritarian and more inventive and democratic (Ilić, 1999: 141). William Glasser for the needs of the modern school finds a solution in quality education that is not based on coercion and autocratic communication. According to the author, "*a successful teacher is the one who manages to convince not half or three quarters but all of his or her students to do well in school.*" (Glasser, 1994: 25).

Quality school has six conditions for quality work (Glasser, 1999: 36) as follows:

1. Class environment should be enjoyable and stimulating
2. The students should be asked to work only on something useful
3. The students are asked to do their best
4. The students are asked to evaluate and improve their work
5. Quality work always feels good
6. Quality work is never destructive

Quality school requires quality teachers. There is a wide range of tasks to be carried out by a modern teacher: new teaching programs, new teaching strategies, new student role, the use of different sources of knowledge, training students for permanent education (Stevanović and Ajanović, 1998, p.138).

Jersild classified teachers' characteristics "*that students love most*":

- Human qualities: kindness, cheerfulness, naturalness, sociability, good humor, sense of humor
- Quality related to the attitude of teachers to discipline: that the teacher is just, stable, disciplined, impartial
- Physical qualities: physical attractiveness, pleasant voice, nice suit, youthfulness, good health
- Teaching quality: good knowledge of the profession, helping the student, acting in the interest of students, to be interesting and enthusiastic, to know how to make the students interested, to teach clearly and to emphasize what is important (source: Ozegović, 2006, p.26).

In addition to students and their parents, teachers are the most important factors of the educational process. We can rightfully say that the quality of future education will depend on the teachers, their qualifications, commitment and motivation. Quality teachers who strive to democratic communication in quality schools and the teaching process are very important but motivated students who seek quality education are as well. High-quality schools, quality teachers, motivated students create democratic communication in the teaching process, and so better success in learning.

2. Research methodology

2.1 The aim research

Concerning this specific topic, the aim of research is to show if there is a significant, statistical connection between interpersonal communication in teaching and students' achievement. The other of this research is to determine whether is achievement statistically better using democratic teaching model rather than autocratic one.

2.2 The main hypothesis of the research

Based on the defined problems, goals and objectives of our research, the main hypothesis is: We assume that there is a statistically significant connection between interpersonal communication in teaching and student success in learning, and that students whose teachers mostly used the democratic model of communication in the classroom achieve significantly better success in learning than those students whose teachers use mainly the autocratic model of communication.

2.3 Respondents

The population from which a sample of respondents was selected, and the population to which this study applies to, consisted of subject teachers and eighth-grade students

from primary schools in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Herzegovina-Neretva Canton). The sample in this study had an element of deliberate, commemorative and simple accidental. The research was conducted on a sample of 423 respondents of which 322 respondents of the representative sample are primary school students, while the other 101 were primary school teachers.

2.4 Instrument

After we created a methodological concept as the basis for an empirical investigation of the problem, we have also made instruments of research. In order to achieve the set goal and tasks, as research instruments, we used: Scale assessment of students and teachers of the dominant model of communication used by teachers and students in the teaching process. Scale assessment we used is the Likert scale in which the respondents expressed strong degree of agreement or disagreement with the proposed claims, in accordance with the proposed guidelines on your usual five-point scale: always, often, sometimes, rarely, never. The survey was conducted during the following period: March-June 2014 in four primary schools of Herzegovina-Neretva Canton, Bosnia and Herzegovina.

In accordance with the defined goal and tasks, with this study we wanted to inquire whether there is a statistically significant connection between interpersonal communication in teaching and student success, and whether students whose teachers mostly used the democratic model of communication in teaching achieved statistically significantly better school results than those students whose teachers use mainly the autocratic model of communication.

3. Results and discussion

Guided by the idea related to our assumption, it seemed interesting to examine whether there are significant differences in the assessment of the respondents on dominant models of communication in the modern educational systems and in the traditional teaching, and consequently we started calculating the value of the t-test. A closer look at the frequent estimates of dominant model of communication in innovative systems and in traditional teaching can be obtained by analyzing the results of the research related to the degree of acceptance of certain claims, i.e. the degree of acceptance of some indicators of democratic models in innovative teaching systems and indicators of autocratic model of communication in traditional teaching.

Table 1: Indicators of acceptance of certain elements of the communication in the modern / innovative systems

Claims related to the model of communication in innovative systems							M
		Always (f i %)	Often (f i %)	Sometimes (f i %)	Rarely (f i %)	Never (f i %)	
1.	Teachers in a clear and interesting way exhibit teaching materials	167 39,5	155 36,6	65 15,4	16 3,8	20 4,7	4,02
2.	Teachers use the modern equipment (projector, Internet, prepared material for work)	76 18,0	162 38,3	108 25,5	56 13,2	21 5,0	3,51
3.	When implementing the teaching content, teachers use:						
	a) new methods of study	112 26,5	157 37,1	104 24,6	24 5,7	26 6,1	3,72
	b) set new problems and encourage students to solve them	77 18,2	159 37,6	111 26,2	27 6,4	49 11,6	3,44
	c) prepare tasks with different levels of difficulty	141 33,3	170 40,2	77 18,2	27 6,4	8 1,9	3,97
	d) suggest 2-3 methods of study and implement the one that most students want	119 28,1	154 36,4	79 18,7	49 11,6	22 5,2	3,71
4.	Teachers encourage students to ask a lot of questions and give their opinion	147 34,6	171 40,4	71 16,8	26 6,1	8 1,9	4,00
5.	Teachers communicate with students' parents only when there is a problem	99 23,4	112 26,5	100 23,6	64 15,1	48 11,3	3,35
6.	Teachers have the ability:						
	a) to build a good and pleasant relationship with students	183 43,3	137 32,4	57 13,5	29 6,9	17 4,0	4,04
	b) to motivate the students to learn	168 39,7	157 37,1	57 13,5	31 7,3	10 2,4	4,04
	c) to encourage individual work and learning	164 38,8	142 33,6	85 20,1	26 6,1	6 1,4	4,02
	d) to provide challenges to students	107 25,3	170 40,2	93 22,0	32 7,6	21 5,0	3,73
7.	During the lesson in innovative systems the teacher encourages students, and respects their different opinions	171 40,4	136 32,2	84 19,9	27 6,4	5 1,2	4,04
8.	Teachers in cooperation with the students provide an environment in which students feel respected as individuals	131 31,0	143 33,8	90 21,3	38 9,0	21 5,0	3,77
9.	During the curricular and extracurricular activities, teachers are rude, ill-disposed toward students and not ready for their proposals	34 8,0	36 8,5	63 14,9	99 23,4	191 45,2	2,11
10.	Teachers have the ability to adapt to students' individual needs and abilities	140 33,1	118 27,9	68 16,1	46 10,9	51 12,1	3,59
11.	During innovative teaching, there is a good and friendly work atmosphere	173 40,9	145 34,3	56 13,2	31 7,3	18 4,3	4,00
12.	The teacher does not commend students when the student knows the answer	50 11,8	85 20,1	89 21,0	109 25,8	90 21,3	2,75

The presented results show that the respondents of the dominant model of communication replied in the following statements:

- That *teachers in a clear and interesting way exhibit teaching materials* 167 respondents agree (39.5%).
- That *during the lesson in innovative systems the teacher encourages students, and respects their different opinions* 171 respondents agree (40.4%).
- That *during innovative teaching, there is a good and friendly work atmosphere* 173 respondents agree (40.9 %).

In addition, they frequently choose the following claims:

- *Teachers encourage students to ask a lot of questions and give their opinion.*
- *Teachers have the ability to build a good and pleasant relationship with students.*
- *Teachers have the ability to motivate students to learn.*
- *Teachers have the ability to encourage individual work and learning.*

A more precise insight into the results presented in Table 1 point to the frequency of the assessment and the selection of statements that indicate the autocratic model dominant in traditional teaching.

Table 2: Results of the assessment of the frequency of elements of the model of communication in traditional teaching

Claims on the dominant model of communication in traditional teaching							M
		Always (f i %)	Often (f i %)	Sometimes (f i %)	Rarely (f i %)	Never (f i %)	
1.	Teachers exhibit teaching materials frontally	63 14,9	151 35,7	134 31,7	44 10,4	31 7,3	3,40
2.	The teacher scolds a student when the student does not know the answer	26 6,1	64 15,1	106 25,1	98 23,2	129 30,5	2,43
3.	Teachers do not like it when the students constantly give their suggestions during the class	31 7,3	44 10,4	102 24,1	127 30,0	119 28,1	2,39
4.	Teachers do not allow their students to suggest anything for their work	30 7,1	60 14,2	72 17,0	115 27,2	146 34,5	2,32
5.	Students have the opportunity to choose and use different sources of information	133 31,4	140 33,1	68 16,1	50 11,8	32 7,6	3,69
6.	During the class the teacher:						
	a) conducts – orders	68 16,1	92 21,7	125 29,6	71 16,8	67 15,8	3,05
	b) encourages creativity - gives opportunity	140 33,1	137 32,4	102 24,1	29 6,9	15 3,5	3,85
7.	Teachers do not prepare for classes adequately. They think they have it all in their head	32 7,6	87 20,6	113 26,7	97 22,9	94 22,2	2,68
8.	The teacher's authoritative approach causes fear, unease and uncertainty in students	33 7,8	65 15,4	121 28,6	109 25,8	95 22,5	2,60
9.	Teachers in their work:						
	a) do not encourage student ideas	52	48	106	90	127	2,55

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		12,3	11,3	25,1	21,3	30,0	
	b) do not pay attention to students' opinions	37	57	105	86	138	2,45
		8,7	13,5	24,8	20,3	32,6	
	c) ask of the students to have to learn every word the way they said it	53	54	72	87	157	2,43
		12,5	12,8	17,0	20,6	37,1	
10.	Students have the opportunity to explain their ideas	160	145	68	26	24	3,92
		37,8	34,3	16,1	6,1	5,7	
11.	The teacher should have a decisive role in the course of teaching	134	140	101	34	14	3,82
		31,7	33,1	23,9	8,0	3,3	
12.	The teacher is the main source of knowledge	124	136	104	35	24	3,71
		29,3	32,2	24,6	8,3	5,7	

The dominance of the autocratic model of communication in traditional teaching is evident based on the presented claims:

- *The teacher should have a decisive role in the course of teaching* 134 respondents agree (31.7%), while 101 respondents (23.9%) believe that the teacher should only occasionally play a decisive role in teaching.
- With the claim that *the teacher is the main source of knowledge* 124 respondents (29.3%) strongly agree, while 104 (33.1%) believe that still the teacher sometimes is a source of knowledge.
- That the *teachers exhibit teaching materials frontally* 63 respondents (14.9%) agree, while 151 respondents (35.7%) believe that that is a common practice and 134 (31.7%) believe that the teachers only sometimes use frontal teaching.

The following claims were also frequent:

- Teachers in their work do not encourage student ideas
- Teachers in their work do not pay attention to students' opinions
- Teachers in their work ask of the students to have to learn every word the way they said it

As we can see from Table 2, the arithmetic mean on the Scale of assessments of the respondents of the dominant democratic model of communication in the modern educational system is higher for teachers ($M = 63,346$) as compared to students ($M = 55,838$). However, this difference is not statistically significant ($t = -8,948$, $df = 221$, $p < 0.05$).

So, teachers and students, on average, have similar assessments related to the dominance of the democratic model of communication in the modern educational system. A group of children on average achieves higher scores ($M = 35,900$) than groups of teachers ($M = 27,29$), when it comes to the assessment of dominance of the autocratic model of communication in the traditional teaching. However, here as well, this difference is not statistically significant ($t = 10,289$, $df = 421$, $p < 0.05$). In other words,

these two groups of respondents express fairly equal estimates related to the dominance of the autocratic model of communication in traditional teaching.

Table 3: Results of the t-test for determining the possible differences in the assessment of respondents (teachers and students) of the dominant democratic model of communication in the modern educational systems and the dominant autocratic model of communication in the traditional teaching

Variable	Respondent	N	M	SD	ΔM	SE ΔM	t	df	p
Assessment of the respondents of the dominant democratic model of communication in the modern educational systems	Student	322	55,838	9,181	7,508	0,839	-8,948	228	.000
	Teacher	101	63,346	6,683					
Assessment of the respondents of the dominant autocratic model of communication in the traditional teaching	Student	322	35,900	7,465	8,603	0,836	10,289	421	.000
	Teacher	101	27,297	6,884					

Legend:

ΔM – arithmetic mean difference,
 t-the value of t statistics,

SE ΔM – standard error of the difference,
 df – degrees of freedom, p –significance

Since the differences in the estimates of the respondents, i.e. students and teachers, did not turn out to be statistically significant, but in order to get a more detailed insight into the results of the distribution of the results of the assessment of the dominant model of democratic education in innovative systems and the dominant autocratic model of education in traditional systems, we have developed a degree of assessment of dominance of these two models with the responses of respondents categorized in the manner presented in Table no. 4.

Table 4: The connection of the assessment of the respondents of the dominant democratic model of communication in the modern educational systems and the dominant autocratic model of communication in the traditional teaching

The autocratic style in traditional teaching	The democratic style in innovative systems			Total
	not dominant	dominant	very dominant	
Not dominant	0 ,0%	0 ,0%	3 ,7%	3 ,7%
Dominant	0 ,0%	62 14,7%	205 48,5%	267 63,1%
Very dominant	1 ,2%	48 11,3%	104 24,6%	153 36,2%
Total	1 ,2%	110 26,0%	312 73,8%	423 100,0%

$X^2= 6,340$; $df=4$; $C.Coeff=0,122$; $p=0,175$

Thus, presented results strongly suggest that the highest percentage of respondents largely opted for the dominance of the autocratic style in traditional teaching and of the democratic style in innovative teaching. The values obtained $X^2 = 6.340$ in the value of the coefficient $C = 0.122$ which is not significant at any statistical level, point to the lack of cohesion among the variables mentioned above, and on the basis of these research results we reject our research hypothesis.

4. Conclusion

Estimates of the majority of our respondents indicate that teachers predominantly use the democratic model of communication in the classroom. Respondents expressed their views entirely agreeing with the statements that teachers always encourage, motivate and reward students for their work, then that the willingness of teachers to help the student affects the positive attitude in the teacher-student relationship, that the teachers are always willing to help the students, and that the understanding and the respect for the students' personalities and teachers' interesting exhibits are important elements to creating a positive attitude in the teacher-student relationship, and that most teachers are always nice to students. Since it is based on attitudes and personal assessment, this research has the character of a snapshot of the awareness of respondents of different characteristics within a certain time period and should be viewed as such.

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